

SOME NEW REACTIONS OF 1-BENZYLIDENECOUMARAN-2-ONES. PART I.

BY T. B. PANSE, R. C. SHAH AND T. S. WHEELER.

Examination of the reactions of *1-p*-anisylidene-coumaran-2-one indicates that the reactions characteristic of the keto-ethylene group exhibited by chalcones are unaffected by the cyclic linkage. Thus one of the bromine atoms in its dibromide, like the halogen atom in the chalcone dibromides, is readily replaced by alkoxy on treatment with methyl or ethyl alcohol. It also undergoes, like chalcones, Michael additions with cyclohexanone and desoxybenzoin and condenses with ethyl acetoacetate.

Chalcones contain an unsaturated keto-ethylene group. The reactivity of this group in chalcones has been studied extensively. Benzylidene coumaran-2-ones also contain a partially cyclised keto-ethylene group. It seemed worthwhile studying with benzylidene-coumaran-2-ones, a number of typical reactions of chalcones in order to find out whether the characteristic reactions of the keto-ethylene group exhibited by chalcones are affected by the partially cyclised keto-ethylene group. The results of the study of a typical *1-p*-anisylidene-coumaran-2-one (I) show that benzylidene-coumaran-2-ones behave like chalcones and the cyclic linkage of the keto-ethylene group does not affect the reactions of the keto-ethylene group.

Thus (I), which contains a *p*-methoxy group in the benzylidene nucleus, on bromination forms a dibromide (II), the bromine atom in which, like the halogen atom in phenyl-*p*-(or-*o*)-alkoxystyryl ketone dibromides (alkoxychalcone dibromides), is readily replaced by alkoxy on treatment with alcohols (see Warrair *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1798) and the resulting product has been assigned the constitution (II, $X_1 = \text{Br}$; $X_2 = \text{O-Alkyl}$) *viz* α -bromo- β -alkoxy derivative.

(I) like chalcones also undergoes normal Michael addition with cyclohexanone and desoxybenzoin (*cf.* Hill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1115) to yield (III, $R_1 = \text{CO}(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{CH}_3$) and (III, $R_1 = \text{Ph} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH Ph}$) respectively.

(I) like chalcones also condenses with ethyl acetoacetate to give a cyclohexenone derivative (IV) (*cf.* Knoevenagel, *Annalen*, 1894, 281, 58). The structure assigned to (IV) is based on the chalcone analogy (*cf.* Rao and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1004) and is supported by its reactions with dinitrophenylhydrazine and similar other ketonic reagents.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

1-*p*-Anisylidene-coumaran-2-one (I) was prepared as described by Herstein and Kostanecki (*Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 318).

Bromination of 1-p-Anisylidene-coumaran-2-one.—(I), when treated in cold chloroform solution with the theoretical quantity of bromine in the same solvent, yielded 1-bromo-1-(ω -bromo-*p*-methoxybenzyl)-coumaran-2-one (II. $X_1 = X_2 = \text{Br}$), m.p. (chloroform), 148° . (Found: Br, 39.1. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 39.0 per cent).

*Action of Alcohols on 1-Bromo-1-(ω -bromo-*p*-methoxybenzyl)-coumaran-2-one.*—The dibromide when boiled with methyl or ethyl alcohol for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour gave respectively on cooling 1-bromo-1-(ω -*p*-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumaran-2-one, m.p. (methyl alcohol), 137° (Found: Br, 22.2. $C_{17}H_{15}O_4Br$ requires Br, 22.0 per cent) and 1-bromo-1-(*p*-methoxy- ω -ethoxybenzyl)-coumaran-2-one, m.p. (alcohol), 145° . (Found: Br, 21.4. $C_{18}H_{17}O_4$ Br requires Br, 21.2 per cent).

*Action of Alkali on 1-Bromo-1-(ω -bromo-*p*-methoxybenzyl)-coumaran-2-one: Formation of 4'-Methoxyflavonol.*—To a hot alcoholic solution of the dibromide (1 g.) was added *N*/10-potassium hydroxide (125 c.c.). The cold liquid on acidification gave the 4'-methoxyflavonol. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 223° (*cf.* Auwers and Pohl, *Annalen*,

1914, 405, 243). Edelstein and Kostanecki (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1509), who prepared it in a different way, record its m.p. as 225°.

Condensation of 1-p-Anisylidene-coumaran-2-one with cycloHexanone.—To a boiling alcoholic solution of (I) (5 g.) and cyclohexanone (10 c.c.) was added an aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (50 %, 10 g.). On allowing to cool the reaction mixture overnight, 1-[*p*-methoxy- ω -(2'-keto-1'-cyclohexyl)-benzyl]-coumaran-2-one separated. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 278°. (Found : C, 75·7 ; H, 5·8. C₂₂H₂₂O₄ requires C, 75·4 ; H, 6·3 per cent).

Condensation of 1-p-Anisylidene-coumaran-2-one with Desoxybenzoin.—The alcoholic solutions of (I) (5 g.) and desoxybenzoin (5 g.) were mixed and heated at the boiling point for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. While still hot, sodium ethoxide (1·25 g. sodium) was added to it. The reaction mixture, on cooling, yielded 1-(β -benzoyl- β -phenyl- α -*p*-anisyl- α -ethyl)-coumaran-2 one (III, R₁ = Ph·CO·CH Ph) in crystalline form. It was recrystallised from acetone, m. p. 243°. (Found : C, 77·5 ; H, 5·4. C₃₀H₂₄O₄, H₂O requires C, 77·3 ; H, 5·5 per cent).

Condensation of 1-p-Anisylidene-coumaran-2-one with Ethyl Acetoacetate.—An alcoholic solution of (I) (5 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (6·3 c.c.) and sodium ethoxide (0·62 g. sodium) was heated under reflux for 4 hours and kept overnight. Next day, crystals of ethyl 2-*p*-anisyl-3 : 4-(1' : 2'-coumarano)- Δ^4 -cyclohexen-6-one-1-carboxylate (IV) separated from the solution. On recrystallisation from alcohol, it melted at 159°. (Found : C, 72·4 ; H, 5·6. C₂₂H₂₀O₅ requires C, 72·5, H, 5·5 per cent). It gives cherry-red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Hydrolysis and Decarboxylation of (IV).—The condensation product (IV) (0·5 g.) was heated with 10 % hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) in a sealed tube under pressure at 160° for 5 hours. On cooling, the contents of the tube were obtained as a sticky mass which was filtered, washed with water and sodium bicarbonate solution. The 5-*p*-anisyl-3 : 4 (2' : 1'-coumarano)-cyclohexen-1-one, so obtained, was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 152°. (Found : C, 78·1 ; H, 5·9 ; C₁₉H₁₆O₃ requires C, 78·0, H, 5·5 per cent).

The compound (IV) also yielded the following derivatives :

Semicarbazone, m.p. (after being washed with hot alcohol) 253° 55°. (Found : N, 9·9 ; C₂₃H₂₃O₅N₃ requires N, 10·0 per cent).

Oxime, m.p. (80 % alcohol), 183° (decomp.). (Found : N, 3·7. C₂₃H₂₁O₅N requires N, 3·7 per cent).

2 : 4 *Dinitrophenylhydrazone* (yellow crystals), m.p. (acetic acid), 209°-10° (decomp.). (Found : N, 10'2. $C_{22}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires N, 10'2 per cent). The *copper salt* of (IV) which was obtained by shaking (IV) in ethereal solution with an equal weight of copper acetate in aqueous solution for 6 hours had, after being washed with hot water, a melting point of 210°. It is soluble in benzene. [Found : Cu, 7'6. $(C_{22}H_{19}O_5)_2Cu$ requires Cu, 7'9 per cent.]

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PHARMACOLOGY DEPARTMENT,
SETH G.S. MEDICAL COLLEGE, BOMBAY.
AND
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ROYAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY.
AND
STATE LABORATORY, DUBLIN, IRE.

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